

ISic3472

I.Sicily inscription 3472

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

contrada Falabia, 10km from Palazzolo Acreide

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336061

1. [— — —]ΕΤΙΑΙΤΕΙΔΕΚΥ [— — —]
2. [— — —]ΝΤΩΓΓΝΗ [— — — — —]
3. [— — —]ΝΤΩΜΠΑ [— — — — —]
4. [— — —]Κ.ΑΣΤΟΣ [— — — — —]
5. [— — —]ΜΙΥΠΟΚΑΚ [— — — — —]
6. [— — —]ΙΣΟΡΟΦΑΝΕΔ [— — —]
7. [— — —]ΚΛΕΠΤΟΣΑΝΕ [— — —]
8. [— — —]ΑΣ. vacat
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1268

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 55-57 no.B fig.126

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